

Studies on Copper(II)-tartrate Complex Part I. Copper(II)-tartrate and its Sodium, Potassium and Ammonium Salts.

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A sparingly soluble copper(II)-tartrate, $\text{CuC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$ has been prepared. It behaves as a monobasic acid in aqueous solution due to the reaction,

for which the equilibrium constant is 2.57×10^{-6} . The water soluble sodium, potassium and ammonium compounds of composition $\text{M Cu C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6(\text{OH})^-$ or $\text{M Cu C}_4\text{H}_3\text{O}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ have also been prepared.

COPPER(II)-tartrate system has been extensively investigated¹⁻¹². This paper describes the preparation and properties of copper(II) tartrate and its sodium potassium and ammonium salts.

Experimental

Copper sulphate and sodium hydroxide used were of AnalaR (B.D.H.) quality. Tartaric acid of L.R. (B.D.H.) quality was recrystallised and used. Approximately 0.1 tartaric acid solution was standardised against 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution. 0.1M copper sulphate was prepared. The two solutions (copper sulphate and tartaric acid) were mixed in equimolar proportion and N sodium hydroxide solution was added drop by drop till a turbidity was obtained. It was allowed to stand overnight. The pale bluish green crystals obtained were filtered off, washed with water and dried over fused calcium chloride in vacuo.

The substance also separated out, but very slowly, from a equimolar mixture of tartaric acid and copper sulphate. The substance can also be obtained from an equimolar mixture of alkali tartrate and copper sulphate.

The copper content of the compound was estimated as copper sulphide¹³ and further confirmed idiometrically¹⁴. The tartrate content was estimated in the filtrate obtained after removal of copper sulphide. Hydrogen sulphide was boiled off from the filtrate and the acid content was determined by titrating against standard sodium hydroxide. The analytical data are recorded in Table 1. From the analytical data the compound is assigned the formula CuT , where T represents tartrate ion. If, however, the compound is prepared below 30° and air dried it contains three molecules of water of crystallisation which can be completely removed in vacuum, over fused calcium chloride. The thermogravimetric analysis of the trihydrate, $\text{CuT} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ indicates that

it starts losing water at 35° and all the water is lost at 75°. The water content of the hydrated sample therefore depends upon the temperature at which the sample is dried. Due to this reason the anhydrous sample, CuT , was used in the investigation.

The anhydrous compound, CuT , is stable in air. When heated at 110° the crystals crumble into a powder without loss in weight. If a suspension of solid in water is heated, the crystals become so fine that the solid passes through filter paper. If, however, the dispersed solid is allowed to stand over night the crystals become larger and filterable. At higher temperature the compound decomposes without melting with smell of burning sugar. The compound is very sparingly soluble in water (3.405×10^{-3} g. mol per litre at 31°) but soluble in mineral acids and also in caustic alkali giving a deep blue solution.

Physical measurements and discussion of results

The solubility of the compound, CuT , in water at 31° was found to be 3.405×10^{-3} g. mol per litre. The pH of the saturated solution as measured by Cambridge Bench pH meter was 4.12. Such a low pH of a saturated solution indicates the liberation of acid due to dissolution of the compound in water. When CuT goes in to solution it is probable that $\text{CuT} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is first formed. The proton is obtained either from one of the coordinated water molecules or from the coordinated secondary alcoholic group. Whatever be the source of the proton the neutral species in solution is represented by $\text{CuT}(\text{Sol})$ and the anionic species by $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}^-$. The probable reactions are :

The equilibrium constant of the reaction (2) is given by

$$\frac{[H^+] \times [Cu(OH)T^-]}{[CuT_{(Sol)}]} = K \quad \dots (2-1)$$

For the calculation of the equilibrium constant, the concentration of $Cu(OH)T^-$ can be taken to be equal to the concentration of hydrogen ion. The concentration of $CuT_{(Sol)}$ is obtained by subtracting the concentration of $Cu(OH)T^-$ from the solubility of CuT in water. The value of K thus calculated is 1.73×10^{-6} .

The reaction (2) indicates that the forward reaction would be favoured by addition of base. The compound completely dissolves in sodium hydroxide giving a deep blue solution. To ascertain the exact nature of the reaction with sodium hydroxide, 0.5288 g. of the compound was mixed with 25 ml of water and increasing amounts of 0.072N sodium hydroxide was added. It was heated gently after each addition to complete the reaction and then cooled to room temperature (31°) and pH was measured. The results indicated the compound to behave as a monobasic acid. The slope of the pH curve changed at 34.7 ml of sodium hydroxide. The reaction is completed at about pH 7. The equilibrium constant of the reaction (2) is calculated from the pH titration results.

The concentration of $Cu(OH)T^-$ is taken to be equal to the sum of the concentrations of hydrogen ion and sodium hydroxide added. So long the solid is in equilibrium with the solution the concentration of $CuT_{(Sol)}$ was taken to be constant and equal to that found in water. The mean value of the equilibrium constant is 2.57×10^{-6} or $pK = 5.59$. This value is comparable with the second dissociation constant of succinic acid ($pK_1 = 4.19$ and $pK_2 = 5.57$ at 25°). The value, however, appears to be very high for acid dissociation of secondary alcoholic group. The coordination of the secondary alcoholic group to copper(II) might render the proton more ionisable but it is doubtful if the acid dissociation will be 2.57×10^{-6} due to co-ordination. The varia-

tion of optical rotatory power of copper(II)-tartaric acid system as a function of pH has been studied by polarimetric method¹⁵. Liberation of proton from the coordinated secondary alcoholic group has been reported in the pH range 12 to 14.

The pH titration results indicate the possibility of the formation of the compound $MCu(OH)T$, where M is monovalent metal or ammonium. To verify this, concentrated solution of sodium hydroxide was treated with increasing amount of CuT compound with constant stirring till small amount of CuT remained undissolved. It was gently heated and filtered. Absolute alcohol was added to the filtrate and a bluish solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride. The copper and the tartrate contents were determined as before. The results are given in Table 1. The potassium and ammonium compounds were similarly prepared and analysed. Similar compound with weak bases like pyridine have been prepared¹⁶.

The analytical results indicate the composition of the compounds to be $M Cu(OH)T$, as proposed before. The molecular conductivity of 0.001M solution indicates the compounds to be 1:1 electrolytes. If, however, the sodium compound is dried in air and not in vacuum over calcium chloride, the composition of the compound is $NaCu(OH)T \cdot 2H_2O$. The thermo-gravimetric analysis indicates that the compound starts losing water at 35° and two molecules of water are lost completely at 110°. The compound is highly soluble in water giving a deep blue solution. On heating the solution, the compound decomposes with separation of red cuprous oxide. The solid compound also slowly decomposes on standing and the decomposition product is dirty green in colour and insoluble in water.

The infrared spectra of the compounds were taken in potassium bromide phase. The magnetic susceptibility of the compound, CuT , was determined by Gouy method at room temperature and was found to be 1.89 B.M.

Krischner and Kiesling³ have reported sharp absorption bands at 1750 and 1097 cm^{-1} in the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND MOLECULAR CONDUCTANCE DATA

No.	Formula of the compound	Calculated		Found		μ eff in B.M.	Molecular conductance of 0.001M solution ohm^{-1}
		%Cu	%T	%Cu	%T		
1.	$CuC_4H_4O_6$	30.04	69.96	30.03	69.95	1.89	—
2.	$NaCu(OH)C_4H_4O_6$ or $NaCuC_4H_3O_6 \cdot H_2O$	25.26	58.84	24.96	57.85	—	126
3.	$K Cu(OH)C_4H_4O_6$ or $K CuC_4H_3O_6 \cdot H_2O$	24.12	55.34	24.10	54.37	—	138
4.	$NH_4Cu(OH)C_4H_4O_6$ or $NH_4CuC_4H_3O_6 \cdot H_2O$	25.78	60.05	25.31	59.92	—	146

infrared spectra of *d*-tartaric acid. The former has been assigned to the carboxylic acid groups and the latter to the C—O stretching of the secondary alcoholic groups. In sodium potassium tartrate a sharp band is observed at 1615 cm^{-1} and another medium band at 1460 cm^{-1} . These are most probably due to symmetric and antisymmetric vibration of the carboxylate groups. In CuT compound a strong and a medium bands are observed at 1626 and 1440 cm^{-1} respectively. The symmetric and antisymmetric vibration bands of carboxylate group in tartrate ion have been shifted as observed in dimeric copper(II) acetate monohydrate¹⁷. This shift of absorption bands indicates that both the oxygen atoms of carboxylate groups of tartrate ligand are coordinated to copper as observed in copper(II) acetate monohydrate.

Goulden has reported that in lactate ion, the secondary alcoholic groups has a in-plane O—H bending absorption band at 1275 cm^{-1} which is shifted to 1390 cm^{-1} upon chelation to zinc¹⁸. In tartaric acid a weak band is found at 1212 cm^{-1} and in sodium potassium tartrate a similar band is observed at 1200 cm^{-1} . In CuT compound there is no band at 1212–1200 cm^{-1} . There is, however, a very sharp and strong band at 1350 cm^{-1} . A very weak band is observed in tartaric acid at 1390 cm^{-1} but a corresponding band in sodium potassium tartrate is not observed. The strong band at 1350 cm^{-1} in CuT and absence of band at 1200 cm^{-1} indicate chelation of both the secondary alcoholic groups of tartrate ligand. The C—O stretching frequency of the secondary alcoholic group is observed at 1080, 1060 and 1078 cm^{-1} in tartronic acid, sodium potassium tartrate and CuT respectively. This indicates that two secondary alcoholic groups are similar in the above compounds.

The magnetic susceptibility of CuT being 1.89 B.M. no Cu—Cu bond is expected as found in the case of copper(II) acetate monohydrate^{19,20}. CuT is possibly polymeric with Cu(II) in octahedral coordination sphere in accordance with Jahn-Teller effect.

The infrared spectra of sodium potassium and ammonium compounds are simpler. The salient feature of the spectra is that there are two strong bands at 1615 and 1400 cm^{-1} in ammonium compound, 1618 and 1366 cm^{-1} in potassium compound, and 1618 and 1370 cm^{-1} in sodium compound. The band at 1615–1618 cm^{-1} indicates the chelation of both the carboxylate groups of tartrate ligand. The absorption band at 1366–1370 cm^{-1} in sodium and potassium compound is the inplane O—H bending frequency of the secondary alcoholic group shifted to

this region due to chelation. Besides, the above there is a broad band at 1124–1042 cm^{-1} in the potassium compound and at 1116–1055 cm^{-1} in the sodium compound. In the ammonium compound the absorption band in this region is split into two at 1124 cm^{-1} and 1070 cm^{-1} . These bands are most probably due to C—O stretching of the secondary alcoholic groups. The broad or split bands indicate that the two secondary alcoholic groups are different. It is therefore very probable that only one of the two alcoholic groups is coordinated to copper. If, the absorption band at 1366–1370 cm^{-1} is due to inplane O—H bending of the coordinated alcoholic groups, as reported by Goulden in zinc lactate complex, the hydrogen atom of the coordinated secondary alcoholic group in MCu(OH)T is expected to remain attached to the oxygen atom rather than ionised.

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